

arm cortex-M processers overview

By: Samer Attrah

- ARM is best known for it's RISC processors
- Arm architecture profiles:
 - o Cortex-A (Application): has the highest performance, designed for high level operating system. Such as mobile phones.
 - o Cortex-R (Real-time): Faster responsiveness, designed for high performance hard real-time applications. Such as self-driving cars
 - o Cortex-M (Microcontroller): Smallest/lowest power, designed for discrete processing and microcontrollers. Such as smart watches.
 - o SecurCore: Tamper resistant, designed for physical security. And it is part of the cortex-M family
 - o Some other branches of the application profile is:
 - Cortex-X
 - Neoverse V, N, E
- The arm architecture gained its importance after the thumb instruction set was invented. Which is currently the only instruction set available in cortex-m processors.
- Thumb instruction set: is a 16bit instruction set
- The best cortex-M processor there is right now the Cortex-M7 which can scale to a higher clock speed. Which is an Armv7 processor.
- Cortex-M0+ is the cheapest and the least capable
- Resources are on <https://developer.arm.com>, where you can find the documentation and many other useful guides and software

- The cortex-M processor is aligned for three tiers of relative performance:
 - o High performance: such as Cortex-M7.
 - o Performance efficiency: Cortex-M3, Cortex-M4, Cortex-M33, Cortex-M35P, Cortex-M55.
 - o Lowest power and area: Cortex-M0, Cortex-M0+, Cortex-M23

- Armv8 processors are split into two versions, the first one is the baseline which is developed on the Armv6 architecture, and the mainline which is developed on the Armv7 architecture.